

WATERPROOF CONCRETE

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Abstract

Getting high-strength concrete in countries all over the world is becoming a major issue. The usage of fire-resistant concrete for medium-sized structures is currently on the rise due to the shift in the ecological atmosphere. As a result, the amount of services that our facilities provide to the public is drastically declining. This concrete won't last very long if we supply it. Waste water won't be used in these concrete parking lots. This concrete fractures easily and has a capillary porous structure

KEY WORDS: Sand concrete, modification, ready suspension

Although there is now a low need for concrete in the countries for water transfer, the significance of the material varies depending on where it is used. Concrete is being used for water transfer in a number of nations worldwide. In locations where water collects, concrete application of water transfer is frequently utilized. This concrete is made up of various aggregates.

Concrete is used for water transfer in the following locations: water collected on a building's roof, areas where cars are parked in public spaces, and construction materials. If concrete is left for water transfer in the appropriate locations, it can also be used to remove water collected on roadside areas. We will guard against environmental factors including corrosion, degradation, and structural alterations causing harm to the structure.

We utilize water-resistant cement instead of regular cement when adding to this concrete.

Depending on the type of concrete needed, it is important to control the lower concrete coefficients for the foundation:

When using M 400 type cement,

1 kg of cement 2 - 2.7 kg of sand,

3, 5 - 4, 8 kg of crushed stone ratio,

M 500 cement-based concrete,

1 kg of cement,

2.4 - 3.5 kg of sand,

4, 5 - 5, 5 kg of crushed stone should be included.

S/c = 0.6%

Cement - 384, 12 kg (cement 32, 5, GOST 31108)

Water - 230 L (GOST 23732)

Sand - 1385, 88 kg (GOST 8736)

Additive- 1,536 L

Keramzite - 692, 94 kg (GOST - 8736)

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